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The Portrayal of Sisterhood: Exploring Female Bonds in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's Short Stories

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Abstract:

The central topic of this paper is to understand and examine how female bonding is portrayed in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's writing, with a focus on the short stories "The Headstrong Historian" and "A Private Experience." This study investigates the emotional, social, and psychological bond that women form to cope with patriarchy. Both these narratives navigate the cultural change and displacements in different socio-political contexts. These stories demonstrate how strong bonds and friendships empower women to face and resist difficult forces with great strength. This paper points out that, while the bonds between women are valued, they sometimes come up with complexities, obstacles, and are not always free from tension. This study also explores how Adichie's works connect to the broader themes of African feminist and postcolonial literature in an intertextual way.

Keywords: Female Bond, Friendship, Identity, Sisterhood, Solidarity.

Introduction:

African literature evolves as a dynamic field that continues to present the continent's history, various cultures, and diverse nature, along with contemporary challenges. Women writers from

Africa play a very significant role in redefining African literature by presenting alternative perspectives in the male-dominated society and discourses. Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie is one of the most influential, acclaimed, and leading African writers of the present time. Adichie always keeps exploring the idea of gender, feminism, and identity in postcolonial dimensions. She uses her beautiful language and eloquent storytelling to link the experiences of Africa with the people of the West. There is a special focus in her works that also depicts the intricate relationships between women, highlighting the idea of how women rely on one another for survival.

Adichie's writings portray female bond and solidarity that becomes a significant component in coping with various challenges. This paper aims to study female relationships and how they are represented in two of Adichie's short stories: "The Headstrong Historian" and "A Private Experience." Both of these stories are part of her anthology of poems called *The Thing Around Your Neck* (2009). Adichie reflects on the idea of how women survive with struggles and hardships against cultural barriers, oppression, distress, and crisis by relying primarily on one another's emotional and mutual support. Adichie, as a writer, has the unique ability to write about personal yet universal challenges in her stories, which have a long-lasting influence on the readers. Drawing from other African feminist writings, this paper also presents special attention to the female bond, which becomes necessary in such societies.

Literature Review:

Women in African literature form a unity of strength through mutual understanding, sisterhood, and solidarity to resist the long-established structure of patriarchy and colonialism. They also share the difficulties for which they have often been oppressed and marginalized. It is all about looking at the emotional bond that they share among themselves. This emphasizes not only the mutual support but also the act of care and empathy that ties them together for collective

empowerment. The portrayal of female bond also extends the biological relations. It encompasses women from different backgrounds to take part in a collective action, shared roles, and responsibilities against oppression and struggles.

Scholars in feminist studies have frequently discussed the significance and power of women, as a form of resistance. Unlike Western feminism, African feminism, or ‘womanism’, a term coined by Alice Walker, considers the difficulties of African women who encounter the challenges and struggles within their communities and cultural contexts. For instance, Bell Hooks remarks that women often find safety and security in each other’s company. This relationship acts as a refuge from patriarchal oppression. In her famous work, *Feminist Theory: From Margin to Center* (1984), Bell Hooks becomes critical because there was a falsity in the representation of the early feminist movement. This can be termed as ‘false sisterhood’, as they promoted unity that deliberately ignored the fundamental differences between women, by prioritizing the concerns of white, privileged feminists. Therefore, Hooks asserts, “Women in lower class and poor groups, particularly those who are non-white, would not have defined women's liberation as women gaining social equality with men since they are continually reminded in their everyday lives that all women do not share a common social status” (Hooks 18). So, here Hooks tries to highlight that Sisterhood cannot exist until and unless we accept that women do not have the same struggles, because some women are more oppressed than others. Solidarity, thus, in its true sense, should always acknowledge the different faces of struggle and oppression. Hooks further explains in her essay “Sisterhood: Political Solidarity between Women” that “The shift away from an emphasis on Sisterhood has occurred because many women, angered by the insistence on 'common oppression', shared identity, sameness, criticized or dismissed feminist movement altogether” (Hooks 127).

Instead of accepting the Western feminist ideas about Third World women, Chandra Talpade Mohanty puts a critique on the generalization of the Western feminist view. She asserts that

how women around the world face oppression. In *Feminism Without Borders: Decolonizing Theory, Practicing Solidarity* (2003), Mohanty offers a framework to understand how solidarity and sisterhood work among women across different contexts, be it cultural, racial, economic, political or even personal: "The assumption of women as an already constituted, coherent group with identical interests and desires, regardless of class, ethnic, or racial location, or contradictions, implies a notion of gender or sexual difference or even patriarchy that can be applied universally and cross-culturally" (Mohanty 21). Therefore, her work challenges the idea of "universal sisterhood" by putting an argument that solidarity and sisterhood among women must be built on acknowledging the differences, addressing the inequalities to destabilize power hierarchies: "I define solidarity in terms of mutuality, accountability, and the recognition of common interests as the basis for relationships among diverse communities. Rather than assuming an enforced commonality of oppression, the practice of solidarity foregrounds communities of people who have chosen to work and fight together" (Mohanty 7).

According to African feminist scholars, for example, Molara Ogundipe-Leslie and Ifi Amadiume, they have contributed a parallel view of pre-colonial and contemporary African society. They state that sisterhood and solidarity among African women are mainly formed and shaped by their cultural traditions and socio-political realities. Therefore, the portrayal of women in the African literary context has significantly evolved. It also reflects the continent's cultural, social, and political dimensions. In her poems, Amadiume addresses the theme of love, desire, and female bonds. Many of her poems often describe close emotional connections between women in African societies, highlighting the different ways of celebrating the bond and friendship that can transcend into a deep and faithful relationship. She depicts how women are woven together like the roots of a tree, sharing pain as well as pleasure with each other.

Molara Ogundipe-Leslie, in her writing *Re-Creating Ourselves: African Women & Critical Transformations* (1994), explores the emerging idea of sisterhood among African women. She

emphasizes how a strong bond serves as a means of resisting oppression and develops a sense of empowerment. She introduces the idea of “Stiwanism”, which stands for the social transformations, including African women. This concept advocates that African women should be included in Africa’s socio-political and economic progress so that they can collectively shape their own culture and future. According to her, women must recreate themselves, see themselves with their own eyes, and define their problems to seek their solutions. Therefore, her indication can be traced in contemporary society on how women writers pen down to recreate and redefine the idea of African womanhood. She highlights the struggles and hardships on one hand, finding strength and agency on the other.

In this way, Adichie’s writings bring out the quintessence of female bonds and their strong friendships, aligning with these theoretical perspectives. She explores how her female characters often find strength through mutual support and collective experiences. In *Gender in African Women’s Writing: Identity, Sexuality, and Difference* (1997), Juliana Makuchi Nfah-Abbenyi also explores how the writing of African women creates a space where female characters do not merely resist patriarchal oppression but also forge alliances with other women to redefine the meaning of solidarity. This idea suggests that the sense of sisterhood in African literature does not only come up by facing adversity and oppression but also by engaging in active support and shared resistance, both in domestic and public spheres. Therefore, this study explores these areas by focusing on how female bonds and friendships become a significant part in Adichie’s short stories and extend to the broader feminist literary fields.

Exploration of Female Bonds:

1. The Headstrong Historian:

The first story in the above context is “The Headstrong Historian”, which addresses the ideas of colonialism, trauma across generations, and female empowerment. This story focuses on

three generations of an Igbo family in pre-colonial and colonial Nigeria. Out of love, Nwamgba marries Obierika; however, her life becomes challenging after her husband's premature death. Later, she also finds it hard to control her son, Anikwenwa, who is sent to a Christian missionary school. As the story progresses, under the influence of colonialism, Anikwenwa embraces Christianity, accepts the ways of life of the British missionaries, abandons the traditional customs of the Igbo, and gradually loses touch with his mother. Nevertheless, the story of Nwamgba continues through her granddaughter, Grace, who later returns as a historian and reconnects with the roots of her family. Grace reclaims the narratives of her people and continues the legacy of her grandmother.

Adichie depicts sisterhood as an effective tool of resistance and survival, either through friendships, maternal care, or intergenerational bonding. It critiques the constraints of patriarchy and emphasizes the strength of female alliances. In addition to that, this sisterhood is not confined to biological relationships; it goes beyond time, culture, and ancestral memory. These bonds can be traced through the study of the story as:

- **Maternal Solidarity:** It can be seen in the story that Nwamgba is quite attached to her mother. In this patriarchal Igbo society, her mother prepares her well with all dimensions, aspects, and realities about life. From the beginning of the story, the life of Nwamgba is situated within the framework of Igbo women who consistently fulfil the traditional roles within their society. Her mother always wishes her good fortune, hoping she can aspire to a better life. Before she got married, her mother told her that life is always uncertain; thus, she has to be prepared for difficult situations. Her mother tells her, especially when Nwamgba informs her mother that she wants to marry Obierika: "She told her mother that this was the man she would marry. Her mother was aghast. Did Nwamgba not know that Obierika was an only child, that his late father had been an only child whose wives had lost pregnancies and buried babies? Perhaps

somebody in their family had committed the taboo of selling a girl into slavery and the earth god Ani was visiting misfortune on them. Nwamgba ignored her mother” (Adichie 105). This shows how women impart wisdom to the younger generations, which gives them strength and the power of resilience. Though, in the story, Nwamgba feels both the happiness and pain of motherhood at the same point in time. Simultaneously, due to colonial education, Nwamgba experiences that her son, Anikwenwa, loses his cultural values, which leads to a generational rupture. This reminds me of *The Joys of Motherhood* (1979), where Emecheta places the identity of Nnu Ego, who is deeply rooted in her role as a mother. In contrast, Nwamgba is disillusioned when she realizes that motherhood, instead of bringing happiness in her life, only brings sacrifices and difficulties, especially in a colonial Nigerian society.

- **Female Friendship:** After the death of her husband, Nwamgba experiences hostility from her in-laws. She seeks emotional and social support from her female friends. This idea suggests the role and importance of female bonding and its essential need in patriarchal societies: “...the abominations they were heaping on the land by cheating a widow, until the elders asked them to leave her alone. She complained to the Women’s Council, and twenty women went at night to Okafo and Okoye’s home, brandishing pestles, warning them to leave Nwamgba alone” (Adichie 107). As in *The Joys of Motherhood* (1979), Nnu Ego gets support from other women to overcome the obstacles of marriage and economic sustenance. It represents a way of comforting and understanding each other at the time of crisis, where they share both happiness and sorrow. This idea can also be traced when Nnu Ego and Adaku, despite being co-wives, experience the very essence of understanding, especially when they face social, political, and economic hardships.

- **Intergenerational Support:** The most significant act of female bonding relies on the emotional attachment between Nwamgba and her granddaughter, Grace, who is later renamed Afamefuna. In contrast to her son, who adopts colonial culture in his life, Afamefuna embraces her grandmother's Igbo culture and heritage. Although divided by time, upbringing, and shaped according to the different views of the world, Nwamgba lives with the spirit of the indigenous tradition of the past. Later, her granddaughter Grace eventually becomes a part of the life of her grandmother, who ultimately returns to history and fulfils her grandmother's legacy by reclaiming the identity of culture. The symbolic name "Afamefuna - My name will not be lost" (Adichie 112) reconnects her to her grandmother's hardships and struggles to retain their cultural heritage and legacy. The stories of her grandmother carry the rhythms of their cultural heritage. Nwamgba wants her granddaughter to remain constantly connected with her ancestral roots despite the colonial influence. One such crucial moment occurs when Grace rejects her baptismal name, "It was Grace who, feeling an odd rootlessness in the later years of her life, surrounded by her awards, her friends, her garden of peerless roses, would go to the courthouse in Lagos and officially change her first name from Grace to Afamefuna" (Adichie 114). This act of renaming stands as a conscious rejection of colonial identity and further upholds the essence of matrilineal memory through the awakening of Afamefuna. The initial name, 'Grace', symbolizes the colonial assimilation and Christian conversion, whereas the second name, 'Afamefuna', affirms pride in native cultural identity. The process of naming becomes a pivotal act of bonding and remembrance. It anchors Afamefuna into a lineage of memory and female resistance. In the course of her scholarly work, Afamefuna extends her resistance from an indigenous perspective and engages in documenting the history of the Igbo, which Nwamgba originally started. Her effort as a historian is not merely

academic, rather, it is a reclamation of the unwritten and unrecorded history, not only of her grandmother but also of those women who had been forgotten like her grandmother. Her actions present her deep and empathic connection with Nwamgba in terms of her struggles and aspirations. She takes up the stories of her grandmother, turning them into a book called “Pacifying with Bullets: A Reclaimed History of Southern Nigeria” (Adichie 114). By writing the stories of the untold and forgotten women, Afamefuna creates an imagined sisterhood in which the voices of women in Africa who were once not heard and discarded from written history, now finally, are heard: “on that day as she sat at her grandmother’s bedside in the fading evening light, Grace was not contemplating her future. She simply held her grandmother’s hand, the palm thickened from years of making pottery” (Adichie 114).

Therefore, “The Headstrong Historian” stands as a multilayered, powerful force that reconnects African women across three generations. Adichie creates a multi-generational view of sisterhood. The act of remembrance with cultural inheritance evolves through the dynamic relationship between Nwamgba and Afamefuna, which is beyond companionship. This relationship, as a result, opposes not only the patriarchal oppression but also the consequences of colonialism. In doing so, Adichie rewrites history. She not only recreates a new definition but also redefines what it means to be reconnected in the time of cultural loss and collective trauma.

2. A Private Experience:

The second story in this context is Adichie’s “A Private Experience”, in which she discovers the profound engagement of sisterhood and female bonding. This particular narrative explores an interaction between two women; the first one is an Igbo Christian called Chika, and the other one is an unnamed Hausa Muslim. When the outside world is completely lost and filled with

so much hatred, both of these two women find refuge together in each other's company during the ethnic riot that takes place in Kano, Nigeria. Nurtured by the relationship of mutual care and protection, they develop an intimate connection despite their ethical and religious differences. The story highlights such female connections that can transcend social divisions. It also demonstrates how women gradually develop a tendency to unite and support one another through the depiction of small gestures, even in the most unexpected places.

Adichie describes female relationships in terms of a powerful act of resistance against violence and social divisions. These bonds are featured in the story in various modalities:

- **Acts of Care:** From the beginning of the story, the two women quickly develop a sense of trust despite their initial unfamiliarity. As a result of the riot, the Hausa woman shows an act of guidance to Chika to seek shelter in a nearby shop. Even amid chaos, instead of an immediate escape, the Hausa woman's ethics stand for protection to save another woman. This signifies their relationship, which is built on mutual care. The two women are stripped of their religious, ethnic, and social identities and depend entirely on each other to feel safe and secure in the private place of that abandoned shop. Additionally, both Chika and the woman have their families outside. On one hand, Chika has her sister Nnedi, and on the other, the woman has her daughter Halima. The sense of understanding comes out when the Muslim Hausa woman asserts, "Allah keep your sister and Halima in a safe place" (Adichie 29). This line encapsulates the essence of her intimacy and forms the central understanding of their relationship. Though it is a nameless relationship, it acts as a backbone in the most affected way. The intimate bond of these two women inside the shop stands in contrast with the violence of the outside world. It portrays how female bonding becomes a counter-narrative to public hatred and violence. When Chika goes out of the shop in search of her lost sister, she gets injured. The Hausa woman opens her scarf, which stands for a religious symbol, and

immediately starts cleaning the wound of Chika: “She wets one end of her scarf at the tap and cleans the cut on Chika’s leg, then ties the wet scarf around it, knotting it at the calf” (Adichie 30). This incident becomes a symbolic act because it not only represents physical care but also emotional comfort. The act of care while treating the wound is tender and maternal, emphasizing how friendship, sisterhood, solidarity, and female bonding are expressed and represented with the ethics of care and empathy. At the moment of crisis, the scarf of the Hausa Muslim woman becomes a symbolic gesture of unity and solidarity that breaks all the religious, ethnic, social, and political barriers.

- **Trust and Empathy:** In the same light, when the riot is taking place outside, Chika, in company with the Muslim woman, hears her as she is filled with grief about her missing daughter during the violence. Though both of them come from different backgrounds, Chika still does not refuse to hear the pain of the Hausa woman. Instead, she accompanies her with silent companionship. This recognition represents the very essence of silence, where words are not even necessary to understand a moment of sorrow. Silence even plays a crucial role in realizing a situation more intensely: “The woman starts to cry. She cries quietly, her shoulders heaving up and down, not the kind of loud sobbing that the women Chika knows do, the kind that screams *Hold me and comfort me because I cannot deal with this alone*. The woman’s crying is private, as though she is carrying out a necessary ritual that involves no one else” (Adichie 29). Chika is willing to express something to assure this woman, yet she does not know what to say. Both of these women have no choice but to depend on each other in this violent space. Their unexpected relationship is based on empathy and mutual trust to survive in this vulnerable situation. The interaction between them encapsulates gestures of care that transcend the limits of verbal communication. This empathic nature in their relationship becomes significant as they can feel each other’s pain and can reconnect

through a shared suffering. This idea reflects an intense understanding between Chika and the Hausa Muslim woman, who shares a strong bond even at the time of loss and uncertainty. Through the intense interaction between these two women, Adichie reflects how a strong bond of empathy, care, trust, and friendship emerges in such crucial moments, which has the potential to transcend social divisions and conflicts.

- **Strength in the form of Resistance:** The strong bond of sisterhood and solidarity between Chika and the Hausa woman serves as a form of resistance in a society that is fractured with ethnic and religious violence. Although the riot is happening outside and is charged with violence and social divisions, their interaction in the abandoned shop stands as a symbol of unity and togetherness. She has never seen an actual dead human body before: “Chika has not reached the end of the second street, toward the market, when she sees the body. She almost doesn’t see it, walks so close to it that she feels its heat. The body must have been very recently burned. The smell is sickening, of roasted flesh, unlike that of any she has ever smelled” (Adichie 30). This brings out the initial detachment of Chika because she comes from a different background. However, the situation of the story juxtaposes the experience and position of Chika in contrast with the Hausa woman, who is accustomed to these kinds of sufferings and loss. For Chika, this relationship becomes a source of emotional support, which demonstrates how women find strength in the company of each other, especially in times of unexpected and violent situations. This strong bond becomes a form of resistance and counter-narrative to this socio-political hatred and religious segregation. By the end of the riot, both of these women realize that they will probably not see each other again. However, the effect and impact of their relationship will remain, and it will continue through their memories. The formation of female bonds, thus, highlights how these moments of

sisterhood are often invisible in the public domain, suggesting that even small but effective interactions have the potential to shape socio-political and moral dimensions.

Therefore, “A Private Experience” conveys a strong sense of sisterhood, emerging not only from an unexpected encounter between two women but also as an embodiment of an empathic and emotional bond. Adichie upholds the transformative strength of female bonding as a compelling and ethical counter-narrative to social and political conflicts. Set against the backdrop of religious differences, this narrative highlights how women transcend social divisions through emotional connections, expressed in gestures of empathy and care. Adichie makes the story a document of female solidarity, and encourages readers to reexamine the relationship within both personal and public spaces.

In addition to that, Tsitsi Dangarembga’s work *Nervous Conditions* (1988) examines how African women face the constraints of patriarchal oppression, colonialism, socio-political, and economic difficulties. This novel highlights how a strong bond of shared experiences allows women to stand as a source of empowerment against all those limitations that are imposed on them by society. In the story, the relationship between Tambu and Nyasha represents their mutual support and resistance in colonial Rhodesia (modern-day Zimbabwe). The protagonists of the novel, Tambu and her cousin Nyasha, share a significant bond that represents the evolving feminist consciousness. Nyasha’s perspective on colonial constraints as well as gender roles is much more critical. This novel also encapsulates how both of these two women are emerging out of the idea that true freedom requires both individual and collective efforts to challenge patriarchal constraints and oppressive societal power structures.

Conclusion:

Though Adichie’s stories show how female friendship and solidarity turn out to be a pivotal bond, she also points out their limitations. Women in her stories do not support each other

immediately. The fact is that the process of solidarity itself needs time; it is not just an automatic response. Adichie's stories encapsulate sisterhood as a vital force of empowerment, resistance, and emotional resilience. Adichie's writings represent the emotional connections shared by women – whether through familial bond, friendship, or even a very brief moment of understanding. This vitality serves as a strength and a counterforce against oppression, alienation, and conflict. In her stories, when a few women often struggle in a particular situation, the voices of other women then come out and encourage them towards self-awakening.

Therefore, Adichie's short stories explore how women rely on each other and create a strong bond to deal with patriarchal oppression, emotional crisis, and socio-political hardships. Both the stories "The Headstrong Historian" and "A Private Experience" illustrate how women find strength in each other's support, especially in difficult situations. Adichie's writings reverberate with other African feminist works to illustrate how female bonding and solidarity emerge in different cultures and socio-political contexts. Hence, this research paper demonstrates how female solidarity becomes necessary for survival, operating across different cultural contexts. Adichie's works, in this regard, become essential in recent academic fields as they focus on female relationships as a means of resistance. Moreover, her writings also contribute to recent feminist studies that highlight the emerging dimensions to shape the agency and empowerment of women.

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